

Semantic Components of English Directive Speech Act Verbs (Order, Command, Instruct)

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ABSTRACT: This research focuses on synonymous English speech act verbs that mean "giving order" (directive). The verbs analyzed in this study are those with very close synonymy, namely order, command, and instruct. The aim of this research is to describe in more detail the semantic behavior of the directive English speech act verbs through their semantic component. This semantics study is qualitative descriptive research. The data in this study were collected by using corpus linguistics and observation methods with note-taking techniques. The data source is the Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA). There are 300 citations for each verb analyzed, which making in total 900 citations analyzed in the study. The study found that the verbs order, command, and instruct has eight semantic features/components that differentiate those three verbs, namely the components of authority, the way of saying, form of order, the duration of orders, level of urgency, actor and undergoer positions, domain of use, compliance level.

KEYWORDS: Command, Directive, English, Instruct, Order, Semantic Component, Speech Act Verb.

I. INTRODUCTION

Understanding speech act verbs is crucial due to their role as tools in the complex dynamics of modern society, particularly in communication, both spoken and written (Wierzbicka, 1987:3). Mey (2009:995) defines a speech act verb as either a term encompassing all forms of verbal behavior or a narrower set of verbs that convey a speaker's particular attitude. Wierzbicka (1987:16) further clarifies that the primary function of speech act verbs is to interpret speech acts, rather than to perform them. Speech acts should not be seen as natural conceptual language that falls under semantics, but rather as language that can precisely express the naming and describing of plants and animals in accordance with their biological reality (Searle, 1979: ix). By adhering to the original meaning, a coherent and well-formed expression is achieved. Moreover, using native meaning tools in meaning analysis can account for the range and distribution of a word, produce appropriate implications, and resonate with native speakers' intuitions (Goddard & Wierzbicka, 2014: 158).

Previously, Wierzbicka (1987) conducted extensive research on speech act verbs using the Natural Semantic Metalanguage (NSM) theory. It was the first semantic dictionary of English speech act verbs. Wierzbicka analyzed more than 250 lexicons which grouped into 37 semantic fields of speech act verbs. These verbs are grouped according to their meaning, with the original meaning of SAY identified as the semantic foundation for all speech act verbs, a notion supported by studies indicating SAY as a lexical-semantic universal (Goddard & Wierzbicka, 2014: 159).

One of which is the directive verb group. This group designates the verb order as the main cluster, with several derivatives such as order, command, demand, tell, direct, instruct, require, and prescribe. Among these, only the verbs order, command, and instruct exhibit a high degree of synonymy and ambiguity, meaning that the use of these three verbs remains unclear and lacks specific boundaries. To date, research on English speech act verbs has not been continued. Therefore, this study seeks to explore the distinctions among the verbs order, command, and instruct through the lens of semantic component theory.

Semantic component analysis is a linguistic approach used to break down the meaning of words into smaller, more basic elements or components. These components, often called "semantic features," help reveal the underlying structure of a word's meaning by identifying its distinguishing characteristics.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The first study, conducted by Kinanti & Astuti (2021) in their article titled Analysis of the Meaning Components of the Word Meaning 'To See' in Indonesian and Javanese (Contrastive Analysis), is a semantic component analysis aimed at comparing

the meaning of the word 'to see' in Indonesian and Javanese. The data used in this study was drawn from lexicons related to 'seeing' in the Big Indonesian Dictionary 'Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia' (KBBI) and the Bausastra Jawa dictionary. The analysis, using a contrastive method, revealed that Indonesian has 16 lexicons for words meaning 'to see,' whereas Javanese has 19. The main difference between the two languages lies in the speech levels found in Javanese, which are absent in Indonesian. Indonesian has 16 lexicons related to 'seeing,' while Javanese has 19, including distinctions in speech levels not present in Indonesian. Both languages share similarities in components like manner and object, but Javanese includes additional levels of politeness and lexical variations.

The second study, conducted by Zulfahita, Yanti, & Purnawati (2019), examines the meaning components of the verb "to hurt" in the Sambas Malay dialect. The primary goal of this study is to describe the classification of meaning components, lexical meanings, and semantic roles related to the act of hurting using hands, tools, and feet. The study employed a qualitative descriptive method, with data collected through interviews, recordings, and observations from the Kokban Hamlet community, Bentunai Village, Selakau District, Sambas Regency. The results show 53 lexemes related to the verb "to hurt" in this dialect, classified into three major groups: 28 lexemes for hurting with hands, 18 with tools, and 7 with feet. Each group is further categorized based on specific actions, such as pressing, pulling, hitting, throwing, stabbing, etc. Examples of hurting with hands include actions like pressing with the thumb and forefinger (*bakkok*) or hitting with the knuckles (*tumbok*). Hurting with tools can involve throwing (*badab*) or hitting with a blunt object (*rimpat*). Hurting with feet includes actions like kicking or stepping on (*pantong*).

The third study, by Girlyastika & Anis (2019), examines the meaning components of the *chamala* verb group meaning "to carry" in Arabic. This research aims to describe the various types of verbs and the meaning components of the *chamala* verb group in Arabic. The method used is the referential distributional method, with data derived from Arabic sentences. The study identified 15 verbs with the meaning "to carry," drawn from Arabic-Arabic dictionaries, web corpora, and the Quran. These verbs were categorized into three types: action-experience (12 verbs), action-benefactive (4 verbs), and action-locative (15 verbs). The common semantic components of these verbs include the action of moving an object from one place to another, with diagnostic components involving the actor, object, manner of carrying, the mass of the object, as well as the state and emotion of the actor. The study refers to the modification theory of Chafe and Fillmore (Cook 1972-1974) for verb types, and Nida's (1975) theory for semantic component analysis. The analysis was conducted based on three components: shared components, diagnostic components, and supplementary components, allowing for a detailed analysis of meaning.

That research is significant as a reference for the study of directive speech act verbs in English because it provides a comprehensive framework for semantic component analysis. By applying a similar approach, research on directive verbs such as order, command, and instruct in English can gain a deeper understanding of the differences and similarities in the underlying meaning components of each verb. This analysis allows for a more accurate and detailed description in distinguishing the meanings of these verbs in the realm of directive speech acts, particularly in terms of actor, goal, and manner of delivering commands.

III. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Semantic meaning components or often also called semantic features explain that each word or lexical element consists of one or more elements which together form the meaning of the word or meaning of the lexical element (Chaer, 2009: 114). To analyze the semantic components, this study refers to Nida's (1975) theory of semantic components. Each word is broken down into its smallest meaning components. Meaning component analysis generally uses a plus sign (+) which indicates the presence of a meaning component and a minus sign (-) which indicates the absence of a meaning component. For example, the word "father" has the meaning components: +man, +adult, +manly, and +married; while the word "mother" has meaning components: +human, +adult, -manly, and +married (Chaer, 2009:114). The difference in meaning between "father" and "mother" lies in the characteristics of the meaning or components of meaning, where "father" has the meaning of 'manly', while "mother" does not have the meaning of 'manly'. Analysis of meaning components can be strengthened by using sentence context (Chaer, 2009: 116).

In order to accurately categorize meaning components, a transitivity analysis of the verbs based on Hopper and Thompson's (1980) parameters is first conducted. This transitivity analysis provides details on the degree of involvement of arguments in an event, such as how strongly the action is transferred from the agent to the object. By examining these parameters, it is possible to assess factors like the volitionality of the agent, the affectedness of the object, and the degree to which the action is completed, allowing for a more precise understanding of the verbs' semantic roles and their contribution to meaning.

The concept of transitivity and the meaning of transitivity refer to the level of transitivity proposed by Hopper and Thompson (1980). Transitivity is traditionally understood as a global property of the entire clause, such that an activity is carried over or transferred from the agent to the patient. And in the traditional view it must involve at least two participants. Hopper and Thompson (1980) introduced ten verb component parameters called transitivity parameters. These components are shown in table 3.1 below.

Table 3.1. Verb Transitivity Parameters Hopper and Thompson (1980)

		HIGH	LOW
A.	Participants	2 or mor participants, A and O A=Agent O=Object	1 participant
B.	Kinesis	Action	Non-action
C.	Aspect	Telic	Atelic
D.	Punctuality	Punctual	Non-punctual
E.	Volitionality	Volitional	Non-volitional
F.	Affirmation	Affirmative	Negative
G.	Mode	Realis	Irrealis
H.	Agency	A high in potency	A low in potency
I.	Affectedness of O	O totally affected	O not affected
J.	Individuation of O	O totally individuated	O non-individuated

- a. Participants: 'Participants' indicates that no action is transferred at all unless at least two participants are involved.
- b. Kinesis: 'Kinesis' involves the transfer of action to other participants within an event. This feature may or may not be present in action verbs.
- c. Aspect: 'Aspect' or 'telic' refers to the status of an event, whether it has occurred or not. This feature is marked [+aspect] for events that have already happened and [-aspect] for events that have not yet occurred or are ongoing. The aspect/telic feature may or may not appear in action and process verbs, but does not appear in state verbs.
- d. Punctuality: 'Punctuality' refers to the brief time expressed by a verb, such that the transition from the beginning to the end of the event is not observable. This feature may or may not be present in action and process verbs, but does not appear in state verbs.
- e. Volitionality: 'Volitionality' refers to the presence of human or animate agency in an event. This feature is only present in action verbs.
- f. Affirmation: 'Affirmation' refers to the affirmative or negative parameter of an action.
- g. Mode: 'Mode' refers to the encoding of an event as real or unreal.
- h. Agency: 'Agency' indicates that participants with high agency can influence the transfer of action in ways that participants with low agency cannot.
- i. Affectedness of O: 'Affectedness of O' is a parameter referring to the extent to which an action transferred to the patient/object (O) is affected. It measures how significantly the action impacts O.
- j. Individuation of O: 'Individuation of O' refers to the difference in status between the agent (A) and the patient/object. An action is more effectively transferred to a individuated 'individual' patient compared to a non-individuated 'non-individual' patient.

After analyzing the transitivity degrees and semantic components of the verbs, the connotations of the three verbs can be concluded as well. Connotation refers to a secondary, hidden system of meaning. It is used to convey thoughts indirectly. Leech (1974: 12-13) argued that connotative meaning arises from an expression that refers to something beyond its conceptual meaning. Compared to conceptual meaning, connotative meaning is relatively unstable, as it tends to change based on culture, time, and individual experience. Barthes, as cited in Hoed (2011:12), suggests that humans do not stop at the level of denotative meaning; instead, they use their cognition through various interpretations, which result in connotative meaning. Connotation operates at a subjective level, often going unnoticed. According to Keraf (1991), connotative meaning is a type of meaning where both the stimulus and the response contain emotional value.

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

This phase of the research is segmented into three distinct stages. The three phases include the provision of data sources and data, the collection of data, and the analysis of data. The type of data in this research is written data in total 900 concordances line that were taken from the Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA). COCA is the first large corpus consisting of several languages that have been designed and built from the ground up in what is known as a “corpus monitor”. The initial phase of the research process involves the gathering of data. The data in this research were collected using corpus linguistics and observing methods using note-taking techniques.

The research's second stage involves the analysis of data. This study is descriptive qualitative research. According to Miles and Huberman (1994), qualitative research data manifests in the form of language-based information rather than numerical data. Data may be gathered through a range of methods (such as observation, interviews, document analysis, or tape recordings) and typically undergoes processing prior to utilization (including note-taking, typing, editing, or transcribing), yet qualitative analysis remains centered on linguistic content. which are typically structured as longer passages of written or spoken language. As for the data analysis method, this research uses an interactive method coined by Miles & Huberman (1994). Interactive research methods include three techniques in the analysis process, namely reduction techniques, data presentation and conclusion/verification.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section discusses the results and discussion of the study. The research findings are divided into three parts: the degrees of transitivity of the verbs, the semantic components of the verbs, and the connotations of the verbs.

5.1 The Transitivity of Verb Order, Command and Instruct

Transitivity analysis details the degree of involvement of arguments in an event, such as the extent to which an action is transferred from the agent to the object. This analysis encompasses several critical aspects that extend beyond argument structure and semantic roles, including kinesis (whether the action transfers), affectedness of O (the degree to which the object is affected by the action), and individuation of O (the specificity of the object). Transitivity analysis provides a richer context for understanding how the meaning of an event is expressed through verbs and the participants involved. It allows for a deeper exploration of meaning variations that may not be evident through argument structure and semantic role analysis alone. Additionally, transitivity analysis offers detailed insights into the progression of an action, its impact, and the relationship between the agent and object, contributing valuable input for subsequent analysis, such as componential meaning analysis. For example, the parameter of affectedness of O helps determine the extent to which an action impacts the object. The following is an analysis of the degree of transitivity of the verbs order, command and instruct.

Table 5.1. The Transitivity Parameter Table of Verb Order, Command and Instruct

No.	Parameter	Order	Command	Instruct
1	Participant	2 (high: A & O) A= Agent O= Object	2 (high: A & O) A= Agent O= Object	2 (high: A & O) A= Agent O= Object
2	Kinesis	+Action	+Action	+Action
3	Aspect	Telic	Telic	Atelic
4	Punctual	Punctual	Punctual	Nonpunctual
5	Volionality	+ Volionality	+ Volionality	+Volionality
6	Affirmation	Affirmative	Affirmative	Affirmative
7	Mode	Realis	Realis	Realis
8	Agency	High	High	High
9	Affectedness of O	O totally affected	O totally affected	O totally affected
10	Individuation of O	O non-individuate	O non-individuate	Individuate

- a) Participant: all of the verb (order, command and instruct) involve two participants in their events. The first participant is the entity acting as the command-giver, while the second participant is the entity receiving the command.
- b) Kinesis: the verbs order, command, and instruct all indicate the transfer of an action through these verbs. This action is expressed through giving commands that aim to alter the condition or status of the object (e.g., someone takes an action after receiving the command).
- c) Aspect: the verbs order and command are more frequently used in telic contexts, as commands typically have a clear and definitive endpoint. Commands given through order and command often require the completion of an action within a specified timeframe, leaving little ambiguity about when the action is concluded.
- d) Punctual: punctuality is a feature that pertains to the time expressed by a verb during the transition from the start to the end of an event. In this context, the verbs order and command can exhibit punctual characteristics. These verbs are often used in urgent situations that require immediate action. Conversely, the verb instruct is typically employed for actions that require a longer duration to complete, making it non-punctual.
- e) Volitionality: this parameter concerns the presence of intentionality by the agent in the event expressed by the verb. All three verbs, order, command, and instruct, involve an element of intentionality in giving commands.
- f) Affirmation: All three verbs (order, command, and instruct) tend to convey a positive assertion.
- g) Mode: all three verbs (order, command, and instruct) are typically expressed in the form of direct commands that state concrete actions or facts.
- h) Agency: in the context of the verbs order, command, and instruct, agency relates to the power or authority possessed by the command-giver or instructor. The individual issuing the command (such as a superior, official, or someone in a specific position) holds strong control and full authority to determine the actions that the command recipient must undertake.
- i) Affectedness of O: for the verb order, the affectedness on the object (O) is typically very high. When someone issues an order, the recipient (O) is required to carry out the action as specified by the command. Similarly, the verb command also demonstrates high influence on O. The actions commanded or instructed with command usually have a direct impact on the recipient, as commands often come from an authority with the power to dictate and affect the recipient's actions. The verb instruct also involves affectedness on O, but this influence is often more focused on the process of carrying out or understanding the instructions rather than on immediate action. Although the recipient of an instruction is affected by it, the impact may not always be as immediate or direct as with order and command. Instructions are generally more informational and often require O's comprehension. In other words, while all three verbs involve some level of affectedness on O, the degree of this influence varies. Instruct is more frequently used in contexts where directions or guidelines are provided without the necessity for immediate or direct compliance. It tends to be more informational or guiding rather than coercive, resulting in a potentially lesser degree of influence compared to order or command.
- j) Individuation of O: the individuation of the object of the verbs order and command typically involves non-specific or general objects. For instance, the verb order is often used with inanimate objects or abstract actions that are non-referential. This means that the object of an order is frequently not a particular individual or entity but rather a general task or item. On the other hand, the verb command generally appears with plural forms or specifies groups/organizations as the object of the sentence. This usage suggests that command often targets collective entities or broader categories rather than specific, individual objects.

5.2 Semantic Component of English Directive Speech Act Verb

Pateda (2001) outlines six crucial steps for conducting semantic component analysis. First, it is essential to identify verbs that fall within the same or related semantic fields. Second, one must document the distinctive features associated with verbs in the same semantic group. Third, the analysis should explore variations among these verbs, considering both individual and collective contexts within the same semantic range. Fourth, distinguishing features must be developed for each verb to identify diagnostic or distinguishing components of meaning. Fifth, the analysis data should be revised using example sentences to ensure they align with the previously identified features and meanings. Lastly, creating tables to outline these distinguishing components helps clarify and facilitate a better understanding of the meaning differences among the verbs.

5.2.1 Semantic Component of The Verb Order

The verb order has the meaning of an action of giving orders that must be followed by another party. In a linguistic context, the verb order implies a hierarchy or authority between the party giving the order and the party receiving the order. This verb is often used in situations where there is a need to regulate or control the actions of others, usually in formal or official contexts. The meaning of an order includes an imperative aspect that requires the recipient of the order to carry out certain actions in accordance with the order given.

5.2.2 Semantic Component of The Verb Command

The verb command can have several meanings that extend across various contexts, reflecting control, skill, and mastery as well as command. In general, command can mean giving orders and mastery over something, be it skills, knowledge, or certain situations. As a giving order, command refers to the act of giving orders to someone else to do something without questioning.

5.2.3 Semantic Component of The Verb Instruct

Specifically, instruct can mean an order, where someone gives instructions to others that expected to be followed. In this context, instruct reflects the act of giving directions with the hope that the person receiving the instructions will follow them exactly. In this dissertation, the use of the verb instruct that is analysed focuses on its use to mean an order. In more detail, below is a table of the differentiating semantic features between the three synonymous English speech act verbs.

Table 5.1. Semantic Component of Verbs Meaning “giving order”

No.	Semantic Component		Verbs		
			Order	Command	Instruct
1.	Authority	Higher	+	+	+
		Similar	-	-	-
		Lower	-	-	-
2.	Way of Saying	Clear	+	+	+
		Not Clear	-	-	-
		Firm/strict	+	+	-
		More Relax	+/-	-	+/-
3.	Form of Command	Formal	+	+	+
		Informal	+	+	+
4.	Duration of Command Execution	Short	+	+	+
		Long	-	-	+
5.	Level of Urgency	Urgent	+	+	+
		Not Urgent	-	-	+
6.	Actor	Animate	+	+	+
		Inanimate	+	+	+
	Undergoer	Animate	+	+	+
		Inanimate	+	+	+
7.	Domain of Use	Umum/sosial	+	+	+
		Certain organizations	-	+	+
		Family	+	-	+
		Military	+	+	-
		Government	+	+	+
		Judiciary/law	+	-	-
		Technology	+	+	+
Medical	+	+	+		
8.	Compliance Level	Must be obeyed	+	+	+
		Optional	-	-	+

1. Authority

The component of authority refers to the power or right possessed by an individual or entity to issue commands or instructions. In the context of these verbs, authority not only determines who issues the command but also how the command is received and executed by the recipient. All three verbs order, command, and instruct involve a higher level of authority. This authority may stem from a formal position or role, recognized expertise or knowledge, or social or personal influence held by the person giving the command. Consider the following data example, where the underlined words represent the actor with higher authority over the undergoer (the recipient of the command).

Data [5-10]

U.S. District Judge Richard Leon **ordered** Brown to spend....
ABB distrik hakim N perintah N PREP meluangkan

‘Hakim Distrik AS Richard Leon memerintahkan Brown untuk menghabiskan...’

(Coca35_web2012)

2. Way of Saying

The way of saying encompasses how the actor issues the command to the undergoer. Generally, all three verbs convey commands in a clear and specific manner; however, order and command are typically delivered in a more direct and assertive tone, whereas instruct is delivered in a more relaxed manner, often in a context different from the other two verbs. The following data provides examples of the use of these three verbs.

Data [5-24]

...the state **ordered** counties to begin assessing trees
DET N perintah N PREP mulai menilai N

‘...negara bagian memerintahkan kabupaten untuk mulai menilai pohon’

(Coca284_news1992)

3. Forms of Command

The three verbs can be used in both formal and informal contexts. This analysis is conducted by examining the sentence context as a whole. This means that each sentence is analysed based on the choice of words used, sentence structure, audience, communicative function, and type of sentence context (academic, TV, web, etc.). Sentence type alone is not the primary criterion for determining whether a context is formal or informal, as not all sentences categorized as formal, such as those in academic or news contexts, necessarily exhibit a formal situation or communicative function, and vice versa. The analysis reveals that, out of 300 citations examined, the verb order was used in formal contexts 261 times (87%) and in informal contexts 39 times (13%). The verb command was used in formal contexts 217 times (72%) and in informal contexts 83 times (28%). The verb instruct was used in formal contexts 228 times (76%) and in informal contexts 72 times (24%). This indicates that all three verbs are more frequently used in formal situations. Consider the following examples: Data [5-19] falls within a formal context found in magazines. Data [5-20] also represents a formal context found in films, as indicated by the choice of language and the audience, while Data [5-21] shows an informal context found in academic settings.

Data [5-27]

...Florida Secretary of State Katherine Harris **orders** all counties
N sekretaris PREP negara N perintah semua N
to finish their recounts...
PREP selesai PRO hitung ulang

‘...Menteri Luar Negeri Florida Katherine Harris memerintahkan semua wilayah untuk menyelesaikan penghitungan ulang...’

(Coca279_mag2000)

4. Duration of Command Execution

The duration of a command refers to the amount of time required for the recipient to execute and complete the given command. The analysis indicates that all verbs generally fall into the category of requiring a short duration, except for the verb instruct, which can involve both short and long durations. This is because instruct is typically used for tasks that require more time to complete or that are more detailed, involving multiple steps in their execution. Look at the data [5-24], Ron Guntz instructed his staff to evaluate a process. Evaluation is an activity that generally requires a longer duration to complete compared to simpler actions, as it involves a thorough process of analysis and assessment.

Data [5-30]

...Palmeri **ordered** the hit
N perintah DET serangan

‘...Palmeri memerintahkan serangan itu’

(Coca171_mov2008)

5. Level of Urgency

The level of urgency refers to the situation in which these verbs are used. This factor highlights the importance of a given command and can influence the recipient's response. Actions required in such situations are deemed highly important and take precedence over other tasks or instructions. Verbs such as order and command are typically employed in urgent situations, whereas the verb instruct is generally applicable in both urgent and non-urgent contexts. In other words, order and command are commonly used when the actor requires immediate results, while instruct usually involves a process that may take longer to complete, making it more suitable for non-urgent tasks. The following are examples of data showcasing the use of each verb.

Data [5-25]

...a federal judge **ordered** the government to speed up reunifications
DET federal N perintah DET N PREP PV reunifikasi

‘seorang hakim federal memerintahkan pemerintah untuk mempercepat reunifikasi’

(Coca170_spok2019)

6. Actor and Undergoer Assignment

Both the actor and the undergoer in these verbs can be represented by subjects and objects that are either animate (living) or inanimate (non-living). Although there is no literal human subject directly issuing or receiving commands, any component that can perform or receive an action can be considered an argument. This is because, in language and communication, inanimate entities are often attributed with certain capabilities or roles based on their context of use. In many cases, technology, systems, or documents can execute commands through instructions programmed or established by humans. For instance, computer software may instruct hardware to perform specific actions such as rebooting or updating. Although the software itself is not alive, it functions as an agent transmitting instructions created by its developers.

Data [5-28]

Schulz **ordered** the American flag taken down before it was torn apart...
N perintah DET N N PV CONJ DET AUX robek terpisah

‘Schulz memerintahkan bendera Amerika diturunkan sebelum dirobek...’

(Coca167_fic2010)

In this context, the flag, as the undergoer, is the entity subjected to the action of the command, rather than being the recipient or interpreter of the command. This is similar to instructing someone to close a door, where the door is an inanimate object and becomes the target affected by the action performed by the actor.

7. Domain of Use

In its application, the three verbs exhibit variation across different contexts. Overall, the verb order is most frequently used in the domain of news (21%), followed by spoken contexts (19%), magazines (14%), fiction (12%), web (10%), blogs (9%), television (6%), academic (5%), and film (4%). The verb command is predominantly used in the domain of fiction (26%), web (20%), film (17%), television (16%), academic (11%), spoken contexts (5%), with magazines (3%), blogs (3%), and news appearing only once (0%). The verb instruct is most commonly found in the web domain (19%), followed by academic contexts (17%), news (16%), magazines (16%), fiction (15%), spoken contexts (8%), blogs (5%), television (5%), and film (1%). Regarding sentence context, the verb order is frequently observed across various environments such as family, social settings, military, government, law (particularly judiciary), and medicine, but is not found in specific organizations like religious institutions. In contrast, command and instruct are often used in religious organizations, among other contexts. Further details can be found in Table 5.3.

8. Compliance Level

Compliance with commands is crucial in the use of order and command, where the recipient is expected to adhere to the directive without question. The verbs order and command typically does not require consideration or approval from the recipient, reflecting the absolute authority of the issuer. Conversely, in the context of instruct, compliance tends to be more optional. The recipient of instructions may have room to adjust or deliberate before acting. The verb instruct often necessitates that the recipient understands or agrees to the instructions before execution, indicating a collaborative element in the process. See the following data for examples.

Data [5-33]

... Airy **instructed** Challis to use the best telescope at Cambridge
N perintah N PREP menggunakan DET terbaik N PREP N

‘...Airy menginstruksikan Challis untuk menggunakan teleskop terbaik di Cambridge’

(Coca22_mag1996)

Data [5-33] implies that before the instruction was given, there might have been specific circumstances leading Airy to command Challis to use the best telescope available in Cambridge. For example, the previously used telescope might have been inadequate for a particular purpose or the results obtained previously might not have met the required standards, prompting Airy to emphasize the importance of this command. In this context, it is also suggested that there is room for Challis to consider the instruction from Airy.

5.3 Connotation of English Directive English Speech Act Verb

Based on the analysis of transitivity degrees and meaning components, the verbs order, command, and instruct exhibit different connotations regarding authority, the manner of delivering commands, and the effects on objects, as well as variations in their usage in specific contexts. The connotations of these three verbs are detailed as follows:

5.3.1 Connotation of the Verb Order

The verb order conveys a strong sense of authority but is more flexible in its application compared to command. While used in both formal and informal contexts, order is often associated with high urgency situations, where the issuer has the power to mandate actions that must be carried out immediately by the recipient. Its connotation leans towards practical and direct obligations, yet it has a broader potential for application, including social contexts that are not strictly military or formal, such as in family settings or everyday professional environments. This also highlights that order tends to be applied to less specific objects, indicating that the commanded actions might be more generic.

5.3.2 Connotation of the Verb Command

The verb command carries a stricter and more authoritative connotation compared to order. It is typically used in more formal and hierarchical contexts, such as the military, government, or religious organizations, where the issuer has absolute authority over the recipient. Commands often leave no room for interpretation or negotiation by the recipient, making compliance highly expected. The connotation of command also implies a need for immediate and unquestioning action. Unlike order, the verb command is often applied to groups or entities, and the directed actions are more directly related to urgent tasks, reflecting a high degree of punctuality.

5.3.3 Connotation of the Verb Instruct

The verb instruct has a more informative and collaborative connotation. Compared to order and command, instruct carries a nuance of being more relaxed and guiding, often requiring the recipient's understanding before the action is performed. Its connotation is associated with providing guidance and instructions, which generally involve a longer timeframe for execution. Therefore, instruct is frequently used in contexts where detailed understanding and implementation are necessary, and compliance is not as urgent. Instruct is also more commonly used with specific and clearly defined objects, implying that the recipient is expected to perform more specialized actions.

In conclusion, there is a significant difference in the "level of power" among the English speech act verbs order, command, and instruct. This is considered in terms of authority, compliance, formality, and punctuality for each verb. Command can be regarded as the primary cluster of those command verbs (order, command, instruct). It reflects that, within the semantic category of commands, command is the strongest and most assertive type, with profound imperative and urgent qualities, making it the preferred choice for depicting command actions in the most intense, strict, and formal contexts.

VI. CONCLUSION

There are four conclusion that can be drawn from the above findings, they are:

1. The analysis of the semantic components of these three verbs reveals eight distinguishing components: authority, way of saying, form of command, duration of command, level of urgency, role fillers for actor and undergoer, domain of use, level of compliance.
2. Overall, based on transitivity, semantic component and connotation analysis, it can be found that there is a significant difference in the "level of power" among the English speech act verbs order, command, and instruct. This is considered in terms of authority, compliance, formality, and punctuality for each verb. Command can be regarded as **the primary cluster** of those command verbs (order, command, instruct). It reflects that, within the semantic category of these three directive verbs, command is the strongest and most assertive type, with profound imperative and urgent qualities, making it the preferred choice for depicting command actions in the most intense, strict, and formal contexts.
3. The use of corpus linguistics as a data collection method in semantic research, particularly in synonym analysis, offers several significant advantages, including:

a) Authentic and Diverse Data

Corpus linguistics allows researchers to access authentic data from everyday language use reflected in various types of texts, such as news articles, literature, dialogues, and social media. This data mirrors the actual use of language by native speakers in natural contexts. In synonym research, this access is crucial because the meaning of synonyms can vary depending on their usage context. For instance, synonyms in academic texts may have different nuances compared to those in conversational language.

b) Connotation, and Usage Distribution Analysis

The connotations of these three verbs reflect differences in levels of formality, authority, and usage contexts, with order related to urgent situations, command associated with power, and instruct linked to structured teaching and training.

c) Efficiency and Reproducibility

Corpus linguistics offers efficiency in data collection and analysis. With corpus analysis software, researchers can quickly extract, filter, and analyze relevant data, allowing them to handle large volumes of data in a systematic and structured manner. Additionally, the use of corpora enhances the reproducibility of research, as the data used can be re-accessed by other researchers who wish to replicate or verify the study's results. Reproducibility is a crucial aspect of academic research, emphasizing the validity and reliability of findings.

REFERENCES

1. Chaer, A. 2009. *Linguistik Umum: Edisi Revisi*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
2. Girtiyastika, T. M., & Anis, M. Y. 2019. Analisis komponen makna kelompok verba chamala "membawa" dalam bahasa Arab. *Prosiding Konferensi Nasional Bahasa Arab V*, Fakultas Sastra, Universitas Negeri Malang.

3. Goddard, C. & Wierzbicka, A. 2014. *Words and Meaning: Lexical Semantics Across Domains, Languages, And Cultures*. New York: Oxford University Press.
4. Hoed, E. 2011. *Semantics: A Cognitive Perspective*. Jakarta: Penerbit Universitas Indonesia.
5. Hopper, P.J., & Thompson, S.A. 1980. Transitivity in Grammar and Discourse. *Language*. 56 (2), 251-299.
6. Keraf, G. 1991. *Diksi dan gaya bahasa*. Jakarta: Penerbit Angkasa.
7. Kinanti, K.P., & Astuti, E.S. 2021. Analisis Komponen Makna Kata Bermakna 'Melihat' dalam Bahasa Indonesia dan Bahasa Jawa (Analisis Konstratif). *Jurnal Kajian Bahasa dan Sastra Indonesia*, vol 10(3).
8. Leech, G. 1974. *Semantics: A Study of Meaning*. Harmondsworth: Penguin Books.
9. Mey, J. L. 2009. *Concise Encyclopedia of Pragmatics*. Amsterdam: Elsevier.
10. Nida, E.A. 1975. *Componential Analysis of Meaning: Semantic Structure*. The Hague: Mouton.
11. Pateda, M. 2001. *Komponen makna dalam analisis semantik: Teori dan aplikasi*. Penerbit Universitas Negeri Malang.
12. Searle, J. R. 1979. *Expression And Meaning*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
13. Wierzbicka, A. 1987. *English Speech Act Verbs*. London: Academic Press Inc.
14. Zulfahita, L., Yanti, L., & Purnamawati, E. 2019. Analisis komponen makna verba "menyakiti" dalam bahasa Melayu dialek Sambas (Kajian Semantik). *Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra Indonesia*, 4(2), 104–109.

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